

SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER BASED NANOCOMPOSITE ACTUATORS

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1 Introduction

Shape memory polymers (SMPs) have the characteristics such as large recoverability, lightweight, superior molding property and lower cost. These advantages have resulted in the SMPs become one of functional materials in various fields. For shape memory polymer of polyurethane (SMP PU), its glass transition temperature (T_g) may be set up at a specified one and its characterizations such as shape recovery and/or shape fixation appear quite different at the temperature above and below T_g . Thus the polyurethane SMP is expected to have wide applications in the field of industry and the composite materials with SMP PU have been developed by our group in recent years [1-8].

In this paper, SMP nanocomposites with several modified carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are developed and their unique characteristics, such as electromagnetic characteristics and electroactive response are investigated for the wider applications in mechanical and electrical/electronic fields.

2 Preparation of Nanocomposites

2.1 Materials and Modification of CNTs

Multi-walled CNTs with diameters of 20-30 nm (purity $\geq 95\%$) and N,N-dimethylformamide (DMF, 99.5%) were purchased from Wako Pure Chemical Industries, Ltd., Japan, and used as received. The CNTs used in this work could be considered as conductive materials because of the multi-walled structure. A resin solution of shape memory polyurethane was purchased in Japan.

To improve the dispersion of pristine CNT,

radical reaction treatment and other mild hydrothermal treatments were conducted. N, N-Dimethylformamide (DMF), methyl methacrylate (MMA, monomer), and benzoyl peroxide (BPO) were used as the reagent in radical reaction treatment.

2.2 Fabrication of CNT/SMP composites

Here, the SMP and CNTs were used as the matrix and fillers, respectively, in the composite. In a typical fabrication, CNTs were dispersed in DMF by ultrasonication for 2 h. A solution of SMP in DMF was added to the suspension of CNTs, and the resulting mixture was stirred mechanically and then ultrasonicated for another 2 h. The completely dispersed mixture was then cast in a mold, and dried at 70 °C. Samples with various CNT loading (3, 7, and 9 wt%) and thickness (0.1, 0.5, and 2 mm) were prepared. For comparison, a pure SMP sample was also prepared. The quantities of CNTs and SMP were adjusted to prepare the various samples.

2.3 Measurements

Conductivities of the samples were tested by the four-probe method using a resistivity meter (MCP-HT450/MCP-T610, Mitsubishi, Japan) as shown in Figure 1. The electrode gap of probe was kept at 1.5 mm, and voltage is 90 V. The diameter of the samples was controlled at 44 mm. Samples for observation were fractured in liquid nitrogen and then coated with a Pt-Pd layer by sputtering, and then observed by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM, S-5000, Hitachi). The

fractured section of layered structure was observed by optical microscope (OM) (VHX-1000, KEYENCE). The dynamic mechanical properties were measured using a dynamic mechanical thermal analyzer (DVA-225, ITK Co. Ltd., Japan). The measurements were performed using the tension model over the temperature range -30-90 °C at a frequency of 10 Hz. Liquid nitrogen was used to adjust the temperature below 0 °C. SE was measured using an EMI SE test system as shown in Figure 2. Samples with a diameter of 12 mm were used to match the holder of the equipment.

Figure 1 Schematic diagram of the resistivity meter used to measure the conductivity of the composite materials.

Figure 2 Schematic diagram showing the system used to determine the SE of the CNT/SMP composites.

Mild hydrothermal treated CNTs were evaluated using X-ray photoelectron spectrometer (XPS). Mechanical properties were evaluated using tensile tester at room temperature. Film thickness is 0.1 mm and cut into dumbbell shape (JIS K6251 7). The data was used to study film's mechanical behavior. Actuator performance was evaluated by measuring the bending displacement of the films using laser displacement meter, controller, digital electrometer

and high-voltage power supply.

Volume resistivity and permittivity of the film were also measured. Space charge measurement was done using pulsed electroacoustic non-destructive test system.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Conductivity of CNT/SMP composites

The conductivities of CNT/SMP composites containing various CNT loadings were determined at room temperature. As shown in Figure 3, the conductivity increases sharply even when the loading of CNTs is low. When the loading of CNTs is 1 wt%, the conductivity increases to 1.26×10^{-2} S/m, about 10 orders of magnitude higher than that of pure SMP. As the CNT loading increases, the proportion that the conductivity increases gradually reduces. When the CNT loading rises to 9 wt%, the conductivity reaches 35 S/m. These results indicate that the CNTs affect the conductivity of the composite more efficiently at a low loading. The increase in conductivity is attributed to the excellent intrinsic electrical conductivity and large aspect ratio of CNTs.

Figure 3 DC conductivity of CNT/SMP composites containing various loadings of CNTs.

In addition, the increase in the conductivity of the composites as the CNT loading increases is consistent with typical percolation behavior [9, 10]. It is believed that when the CNT loading reaches a certain threshold, a conductive network composed of CNTs begins to form in the CNT/SMP composites, causing a dramatic increase in the conductivity to occur around this threshold. In Figure 3, a

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significant increase in the conductivity was observed between 0-1 wt%, indicating that the threshold was a loading of less than 1 wt%. It is well known that a uniform distribution of the filler favors the formation of a network at low loadings. Therefore, the low threshold for conductivity of the CNT/SMP composites confirms that the mixing process involving ultrasonic dispersion provides a uniform distribution of CNTs in the composites.

3.2 Distribution of CNTs in CNT/SMP composites

The distribution of CNTs in the composites was observed by FESEM. Figure 4 (a)-(c) show micrographs of sections of the samples with CNT loadings of 1, 3 and 7 wt%, respectively. The CNTs are uniformly dispersed in the SMP matrix, even when the CNT loading is 7 wt%. The amount of CNTs observed in the images increases as the CNT loading increases. Compared with Fig. 5 (a) and (b), a larger number of CNTs are observed in Figure 4 (c) for the composite containing 7 wt% CNTs, and some are so close that they connect with each other. The Figure 4 (d)-(f) confirm the uniform distribution of CNTs over larger areas of the samples. These images indicate that the uniform distribution of CNTs was widespread in the composites and not limited to a small area.

The dramatic increase in the conductivity of the composites at low CNT loading observed in section 3.1 indicated the formation of a conductive network. However, a CNT network was not readily observed by FESEM, especially at lower loading. This inconsistency could be explained by the micrographs in Figure 4 only showing sections of the samples, while the network is inside the whole sample rather than on these sections.

The uniform distribution of the CNTs should be helpful for forming connections among CNTs even at a low loading, which affects the conductivity of the composites significantly. Therefore, these micrographs that show uniform distributions of CNTs support the improved conductivity found in section 3.1 The FESEM observations also confirm that ultrasonic dispersion was effective for producing composites containing well-dispersed CNTs.

Figure 4 FESEM micrographs of CNT/SMP composites containing various CNT loadings: (a), (d) 1 wt%; (b), (e) 3 wt%; (c), (f) 7 wt%.

3.3 Shielding Effectiveness of EMI

According to Maxwell's equations, an electromagnetic wave is composed of electric and magnetic fields. An alternating electric field generates an alternating magnetic field, which in turn generates an alternating electric field. Therefore, an electromagnetic wave can be considered as a self-propagating transverse alternating wave of electric and magnetic fields. There are two cases that should be considered for EMI shielding, the near-field and far-field. The far-field is defined as distances further than $\lambda/2\pi$ between the radiation source and shielding material, where λ is the wavelength of the electromagnetic wave [5]. In this paper, the electromagnetic wave used to test shielding materials was limited to a plane wave in the far-field. The SE is expressed as:

$$SE = 10 \log \frac{P_o}{P_T} = 20 \log \frac{|H_o|}{|H_T|} = 20 \log \frac{|E_o|}{|E_T|} \quad (1)$$

where P_O , H_O , and E_O are the power, magnetic and electric field intensity when there is no shielding material; P_T , H_T , E_T are the power, magnetic and electric field intensity in the presence of a shielding material.

When an electromagnetic wave propagates to a shielding material, a typical process is as follows: part of the wave is reflected on the surface of the material, which strongly depends on the impedance matching; part of the wave is absorbed, and dissipated as heat; part of the wave is multi-reflected inside the shielding material; and the others penetrate through the material. Based on the description above, electromagnetic wave shielding is mainly dominated by three functions: reflection (SE_R), absorption (SE_A), and multi-reflection (SE_M), giving Eq. (2):

$$SE = SE_R + SE_A + SE_M \quad (2)$$

These three functions further relate to the intrinsic permittivity, permeability, conductivity, and thickness of the material and the frequency of the electromagnetic wave.

The skin depth (δ) is defined as the distance at which the electric field decreases to $1/e$ of its incident strength, which is expressed as follows:

$$\delta = 1/\sqrt{\pi f \mu \sigma} \quad (3)$$

where f is the wave frequency, μ is the permeability, and σ is the electrical conductivity in S/m. The prepared CNT/SMP composites can be regarded as nonmagnetic, thus $\mu = \mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7} \text{ Hm}^{-1}$, where μ_0 is the permeability in free space.

When the shielding material is thicker than the skin depth, the multi-reflection is effectively reduced, especially in the case when $SE_A \geq 15 \text{ dB}$ [26]. Therefore, for a very approximate analysis, the multi-reflection can be ignored, and Eq. (2) simplifies to:

$$SE = SE_R + SE_A \quad (4)$$

According to Al-Saleh *et al.* [29], for conductive materials, SE_R and SE_A can be described as followings:

$$SE_R = 39.5 + 10 \log \frac{\sigma}{2\pi f \mu} \quad (5)$$

$$SE_A = 8.7 \frac{d}{\delta} = 8.7 d \sqrt{\pi f \mu \sigma} \quad (6)$$

where d is the thickness of the sample. According to Eq. (5) and Eq. (6), it is apparent that when f and μ are defined, the reflection depends on the conductivity, while the absorption is determined by both the thickness and conductivity of the material. Therefore, the total SE is a function of the frequency, thickness and conductivity, and is expressed as:

$$SE = 39.5 + 10 \log \frac{\sigma}{2\pi f \mu} + 8.7 d \sqrt{\pi f \mu \sigma} \quad (7)$$

CNT/SMP composites with various CNT loading and thickness were measured for their SE over the frequency ranges of 4-7 and 13-16 GHz. The SE was plotted as a function of frequency to investigate the effect of material thickness (Figure 5). The SE curves were recorded for composites containing 7 wt% CNTs with thicknesses of 0.1 and 0.5 mm.

As shown in Figure 5 (a), the SE of the sample with a thickness of 0.5 mm is greater over the entire frequency range of 4-7 GHz than that of the sample that is 0.1 mm thick. Almost the same pattern is observed for the SE curves of the same samples between 13 and 16 GHz (Fig. 2-6(b)). These results demonstrate that the thickness of the sample had a great effect on the SE, with the thicker sample exhibiting an increased SE. According to Eq. (3), the thickness of the samples (0.1 and 0.5 mm) is less than the skin depth, so the influence of multi-reflection cannot be ignored. Therefore, the dependence of the SE on the thickness could be attributed to both the increased absorption and the influence of multi-reflection as the thickness increases.

Figure 5 also revealed the effect of frequency on the SE of the composite films. For the curves displayed in Figure 5, the SE tends to increase with the frequency, which can be seen more clearly by comparing Figure 5(a) with Figure 5(b). The average SE for each frequency range was calculated to further confirm this tendency. For the sample with a thickness of 0.1 mm, the average SE was 1.92 dB over 4-7 GHz, and this value increased to 4.76 dB

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over 13-16 GHz. The average SE was 8.65 dB over 4-7 GHz for the sample that was 0.5 mm thick, and this increased to 11.35 dB for the 13-16 GHz range. The disparity of the SE between the two frequency ranges confirms the tendency of the SE to increase with frequency.

Figure 5 SE of CNT/SMP composites containing 7 wt% CNTs and film thicknesses of 0.1 and 0.5 mm at: (a) 4-7 GHz, and (b) 13-16 GHz.

The SE of samples containing 9 wt% CNTs was also measured and the results are plotted in Figure 6. The SE curves exhibit a similar trend to those from the composite containing 7 wt% CNTs, where the SE increases with both the thickness of the sample and the frequency. It is speculated that when the loading of CNTs was 9 wt%, the influences of thickness and frequency on SE were still based on the same shielding mechanism as for the composite containing 7 wt% CNTs. The enhanced SE of the composite containing 9 wt% CNTs compared with

that containing 7 wt% reveals the positive effect of conductivity on the SE.

Figure 6 SE of CNT/SMP composites containing 9 wt% CNTs with thicknesses of 0.1 and 0.5 mm over frequency ranges of: (a) 4-7 GHz, and (b) 13-16 GHz.

The SE of samples with a thickness of 2 mm and CNT loadings of 3, 7 and 9 wt% were measured over the frequency range of 13-16 GHz (Figure 7). The SE increases significantly as the CNT loading increases. For the sample containing 3 wt% CNTs, the average SE over 13-16 GHz was 7.68 GHz, while the samples containing 7 and 9 wt% CNTs showed average SE of 17.31 and 28.46 dB, respectively. These results show that the composites with higher conductivity achieved higher SE. A maximum SE of almost 35 dB was realized for the sample containing 9 wt% CNTs at a frequency of 16 GHz.

Figure 7 SE of CNT/SMP composites with a thickness of 2 mm with various CNT loadings (3, 7 and 9 wt%) over 13-16 GHz.

The samples containing 7 and 9 wt% CNTs are assumed to behave as conductive materials. According to Eq. (3), a thickness of 2 mm is greater than the skin depth. Therefore, the SE of these two samples was calculated using Eq. (7) to compare with the experiment results. As shown in Figure 8, the calculated SE exhibits a fairly similar trend to the experiment results for the samples containing 7 and 9 wt% CNTs. However, the difference between the calculated and observed results cannot be ignored. Figure 8 shows that Eq. (7) provides approximate predictions for the SE of 2 mm thick samples containing 7 and 9 wt% CNTs over 13-16 GHz. Without regard for precise measurements, the difference present between the experimental and calculated SE may be attributed to the neglect of multi-reflection and the assumption that the composites are conductive materials.

Figure 8 Comparison between calculated and experiment results for the SE of CNT/SMP composites with a thickness of 2 mm and CNT loadings of 7 and 9 wt%.

3.4 Mechanical Properties of modified CNT/SMP composites

Effect of modified CNTs in polar solvent (DMF) were investigated. All CNTs dispersed well in DMF after mixture. Pristine CNTs precipitated while modified CNTs were uniformly dispersed in DMF. MMA were attached to the surface between CNTs in the radical reaction treatment thus helped it to improve the dispersion. Meanwhile, in the mild hydrothermal treatment, oxygen functional groups were introduced to the surface of CNTs thus helped it to disperse uniformly in polar solvent.

Figure 9 Stress-strain curves with different modifications of CNT surface.

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Figure 9 of stress-strain curve of each film gives that mechanical properties of SMP/CNTs films were relatively improved than SMP film due to the modification. MMA films have higher strain and lower Young's modulus than KOH and KPS films. MMA films are softer and more elastic, which are desirable for actuation.

(a) SMP

(b) SMP/MMA 0.1 wt. %

Figure 10 Bending characterization of repetition loading on actuators.

3.5 Actuation Performance

The films bent when DC voltage is applied, and the bending displacements occurred. The bending displacement was also dependent on the voltage applied and increased as the applied voltage increased. Coated films showed bigger displacement than uncoated films and coated MMA 0.1 wt.% showed the highest. Voltage could be applied uniformly and bending moment was higher when coated. Bending displacement increased with

increasing CNTs content for almost all cases, except for uncoated and coated KOH 0.5 wt.%. SMP/CNTs films showed higher bending displacement than SMP films, and MMA films showed better actuation than KOH and KPS films overall.

The evaluations had been focused on silver-coated SMP and SMP/CNTs 0.1 wt.% films. Repetitive voltage was applied to the films and the result for SMP/MMA0.1wt.% is shown in Figure 10. The films bent to the cathode side when the voltage was applied and reverted almost to its original position but not completely when the voltage was removed. The films are considered as an elastic body and showed elastic recovery when the voltage was removed. The bending displacement of each film was similar with the repetition of voltage. This phenomenon is considered as a kind of memory, where the electric field reminds the films of the electrically memorized strain.

4 Conclusions

In this work, CNT/SMP composites containing well-dispersed CNTs were prepared by ultrasonic dispersion of the materials in DMF. The uniform distribution of the CNTs was confirmed by FESEM observations. The conductivity of the composites depended strongly on the CNT loading, and increased as the CNT loading increased. The conductivity reached 35 S/m when the CNT loading was 9 wt%. The SE of the composites was measured over 4-7 and 13-16 GHz, and the highest SE of nearly 35 dB was achieved for the composite with a thickness of 2 mm containing 9 wt% CNTs. The results indicated that the SE increased significantly as the thickness and conductivity of the composite increased. Furthermore, the SE of the composites was also greater at higher frequency.

In the case of the carbon nanotubes treated by radical reaction and mild hydrothermal treatment, the developed nanocomposites have shown a good mechanical properties and electroactive actuation. They keep high strain recovery ability after repetitive loading cycles. This will lead the developed materials can be utilized for the cycle application with any shape in daily life. Electrical properties of developed films of SMP/treated CNT are discussed according to the volume resistivity and space charge measurement results. In the actuation behavior, the films bent to the cathode side when

voltage is applied and reverted to its original position when voltage is removed. Each type of CNTs modification has unique effects on the actuator performance.

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